

SHORE

Empower students as the agents of change

D6.2. SHORE – Application package

6/12/2023

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F6S

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Executive summary

This document is a deliverable of the SHORE Project, funded under the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101112815.

The aim of this document is to present SHORE - Open Call #1 documentation KIT consisting of the following documents:

1. SHORE Open Call #1 – Open Call Overview
2. SHORE Open Call #1 – Annex 1 – SHORE Guidelines for Applicants
3. SHORE Open Call #1 – Annex 1 .1 - Evaluation and selection
4. SHORE Open Call #1 – Annex 2 – SHORE Application Form
5. SHORE Open Call #1 – Annex 2.1 - SHORE Proposal Template
6. SHORE Open Call #1 – Annex 3 - SHORE Sub-grant agreement (template)
7. SHORE Open Call #1 – Annex 4 - SHORE Declaration of Honour
8. SHORE Open Call #1 – Annex 5 - SHORE Bank account information
9. SHORE Open Call #1 - Frequently Asked Questions

SHORE – Open Call #1

Open Call Overview

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1. Introduction

The main objective of the SHORE project is to enhance the ocean and water literacy of primary and secondary students, educators, and schools, by empowering youth to become agents of change and eco-citizens.

The EU-funded SHORE project will support **100 schools' projects** via **3 Open Calls** and with a **total budget of 900,000€ (max 10,000€ grant per project)** for primary and secondary schools in the pursuit of increasing **ocean and water literacy**, sustainability, and blue economy knowledge among students to mobilise them as agents of change and ramp up the accreditation of the Network of European Blue Schools.

1.1. Background – EU Mission Ocean

Water, universally recognized as a fundamental need and a sanctuary for diverse life forms, serves as the largest carbon sink, a vital transport route, and a global resource essential for numerous functions. The absence of healthy waters would mean no life on our planet.

Yet, owing to human activities, the decline in both marine and river ecosystems poses a significant threat to the health, well-being, and overall prosperity of European citizens and societies. Urgent action is imperative to fulfil the EU Green Deal and the [EU Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030](#). This EU initiative represents a novel approach aimed at implementing tangible solutions to revive the health of our oceans and waters. It stands as a crucial pathway toward achieving climate neutrality and preserving nature.

To support the achievement of the [EU Mission Ocean objectives](#), SHORE project aims to engage youth in the European policies and lifestyle with the help of local life-changing projects integrated into the curriculum of schools to achieve both at the grassroots and international level mobilisation of teachers, schools, students, and local community.

2. SHORE Open Call objectives and requirements

2.1. Ocean Literacy & Blue Curricula: Empowering students as agents of change

The aim of the funded school projects is to **increase knowledge and awareness of ocean and water literacy among students, teachers, and the local community**, by increasing their **active engagement in the project implementation through co-creation process and authentic interlinked activities**.

To do so, schools will be supported during project implementation to **develop and utilise new and innovative teaching and learning resources based on Open Schooling methodologies and Blue Skills Curricula**, which can, in addition to formal educational curricula, successfully expose students to current challenges about water & ocean issues, and Blue Economy in a life-long run.

2.2. The European Network of Blue Schools

To expand and broaden the ocean and water literacy knowledge among children, youth and teachers, the SHORE project supports **the accreditation of schools and their projects within the**

Network of European Blue Schools established under the EU4Ocean coalition. The network's intention is to help teachers make the ocean a relevant part of the school curriculum via the *Find the Blue* challenge, the identification of ocean-based topics relevant to the schools' youth and active collaboration with students in creating a related school project.

SHORE also envisions international and regional collaboration of school beneficiaries through **twinning mechanism**, designed and implemented for exchange of best practices between schools and showcasing successful stories (Please refer to the eTwinning portal to find suitable partners for cooperation: <https://school-education.ec.europa.eu/en/etwinning>).

Therefore, schools applying for SHORE's Open Calls should be accredited members of the European Network of Blue Schools or **aspire to be members of the European Network of Blue Schools and will demonstrate how they intend to meet the prerequisites** to become accredited members by the time of completion of the project.

3. SHORE Open Call Target Areas

SHORE's Open Calls are open for schools legally established and based in the European Union or Horizon Europe Associated Countries from one of the five target regional areas: **Baltic Sea, Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Rhine River, and Danube River Area** (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: SHORE - Open Call #1 Target Areas

4. SHORE Open Call Topics and Activities

Schools' projects funded via the SHORE Open Calls should focus on one of the following **topics & subtopics about blue economy & ocean literacy** (See Figure 2).

Figure 2: SHORE Open Call Topics

The SHORE Open Calls are welcoming proposals which include **different types of activities** aimed at primary and secondary schools' students, teachers and/or parents of the schools concerned. A fixed and exhaustive list of the different types of activities for which a school may receive financial support is provided in the Annex 1 – SHORE Guidelines for Applicants.

5. SHORE Open Call Funding Scheme

By managing 3 Open Calls, SHORE expects to support **100 school projects with a total budget of 900,000€ (max 10,000€ grant per project)**. The estimated funding scheme is divided per each Open Call in the following table.

Table 1: Estimated funding scheme per each SHORE Open Call

Open Call #	Est. budget per Open Call
Open Call #1	405,000€
Open Call #2	315,000€
Open Call #3	180,000€

To promote the participation of minority groups from applicants' communities, SHORE's Open Calls strive to reserve **20% of the available budget for school projects involving migrants or Ukrainian citizens under temporary protection.**

The financial support for each awarded school will be up to €10,000 provided **in the form of a lump sum**, broken into phases as mentioned in Annex 1 - Guideline for Applicants.

6. SHORE awarded projects follow-up

Selected projects are **expected to last up to 6 months**, a period during which all school project activities, as described in the proposal, should be implemented with the funding support received.

SHORE Project partners acting as **SHORE Country Hubs** will mentor and guide the schools and students, about successful Blue Skills Curricula and project implementation. Selected projects will benefit through a permanent contact with their mentors, online meetings for project management and sharing of best practices from targeted regions.

SHORE Digital Platform and “Ocean Ambassador of the Year” Award

SHORE will ensure international visibility and awareness of the projects among the public by creating **its own digital platform**, an open-source virtual learning environment and education management system which will enable the follow-up of student and school projects in addition to publishing developed Blue Skills Curricula materials for school activities and teacher routes.

Schools awarded with the grant will have their own profile created at SHORE digital platform, allowing them to upload their activities & share information about their projects. After each open call period, **an online contest** will be held to select the best school projects through a global competition using the said digital platform, and the voting will be open to the public. After the selection of the global winner, the school will be awarded as **“Ocean Ambassador of The Year”** and promoted as such via the SHORE project website and social media.

7. SHORE Open Call Timeline

The **SHORE Open Call 1** opens on **17 January 2024** and closes on **20 March 2024 at 17:00 CET (Brussels time)**. Proposals must be submitted vis the F6S Platform at <https://www.f6s.com/shore-open-call-1/apply>

After submission, SHORE will begin the evaluation and selection process. Proposals not fitting the eligibility criteria (as stated in the Annex 1 – SHORE Guidelines for Applicants) will be notified. Each proposal passing the eligibility check will be evaluated by an external pool of experts and receive a notification about their final status (rejected or accepted). Selected projects will be invited to enter the contract preparation and signature phase and access the SHORE Programme.

Figure 3 showcases the full timeline and process of SHORE Open Call 1, which will be followed in a similar manner for the other two Open Calls (see Figure 4).

Figure 3: SHORE - Open Call #1 Timeline & Process

Figure 4: SHORE Open Calls Timeline Overview

8. Relevant Links and Information

- Project website, where all official documents are published: <https://shoreproject.eu/>
- The Guide for Applicants and documents, where the rules and procedures of the programme are described (available for download at <https://shoreproject.eu/open-calls/>)
- Open call application form: <https://www.f6s.com/shore-open-call-1/apply>
- Open call support: opencalls@shoreproject.eu
- F6S helpdesk: support@f6s.com
- Network of European Blue Schools: https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/theme/ocean-literacy-and-blue-skills/ocean-literacy/network-blue-schools/become-european-blue-school_en
- SHORE social media channels: [Facebook](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Twitter](#), [Instagram](#)

9. Open Calls documents

SHORE Open Call will be supported by the following documents, Applicants are encouraged to get acquainted with documents before submitting proposal:

- **Annex 1 - SHORE Guidelines for applicants**
- **Annex 2 - SHORE Application form**, an online application form, available at F6S platform <https://www.f6s.com/shore-open-call-1/apply>
- **Annex 2.1 - SHORE Proposal Template**, a template that indicates all the information that should be provided as part of the project proposal and **MUST** be completed and uploaded within the form available on the F6S page.
- **Annex 3 - SHORE Sub-grant agreement (template)**, which provides a template of the sub-grant agreement that the successful applicants will be requested to sign.
- **Annex 4 - SHORE Declaration of Honour**
- **Annex 5 - SHORE Bank account information**, which collects information about the bank account to which payments will be made.

SHORE – Open Call #1

Annex 1 – SHORE Guidelines for Applicants

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1. Introduction

This document provides the relevant information regarding Open Call #1 of the SHORE project. The SHORE – Open Call #1 aims to support student and schools-led projects that can:

- contribute to the achievement of the objectives under the **EU Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030**, among others through development and implementation of innovative solutions and products contributing to those objectives;
- reinforce and contribute to the [EU4Ocean coalition](#) and its European Network of Blue Schools.

In doing so, SHORE aims to engage students, teachers and other actors from the school ecosystem and the wider community to co-design, co-develop and co-implement projects that can contribute to expand and broaden ocean & water literacy.

An overview of the SHORE - Open Call #1 can be found in Figure 1.

• Figure 1: SHORE - Open Call #1 and follow-up overview

Applications for the SHORE - Open Call #1 will be accepted from **17 January 2024** until **20 March 2024, 17h CET**.

After Open Call closure, there will be a period of evaluation, selection and onboarding which is expected to last for a period of approximately 3 months.

The selected school projects will have an expected duration of up to 6 months (**around 20 beneficiaries selected**).

NOTE: The SHORE project has planned the Open Call #1 and projects follow up in a way to ensure that enough time has been allocated to each school project for successful completion. The SHORE recognizes that unforeseen events might occur. To keep transparency and fairness among applicants of the Open Call, closing dates are fixed dates and will only be updated in case of unforeseen events. All other dates mentioned in this document are tentative and may be updated to accommodate specific needs of the applicant and the consortium.

2. Eligibility criteria

The section describes in detail **who can apply** and **what condition should be met by application**. All applicants must meet the requirements described in this section to be eligible for the SHORE – Open Call #1.

2.1.1. Type of applicants

The call will fund projects implemented by **primary or secondary schools¹ legally registered and established in EU and/or HEU Associated countries**.

Any school mentioned above is not:

- under liquidation or is not an enterprise under difficulty according to the Commission Regulation No 651/2014, art. 2.18.,
- excluded from the possibility of obtaining EU funding under the provisions of both national and EU law or by a decision of both national or EU authority.
- declared as bankrupt or have initiated bankruptcy procedures.
- having convictions for fraudulent behaviour, other financial irregularities, and unethical or illegal business practices.
- subjected to EU restrictive measures under Article 29 of the Treaty on the European Union (TEU) or Article 215 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU).

2.1.2. Eligible countries and regions

Each school must be established in any of the following countries to be eligible to participate in the SHORE – Open Call #1:

- The Member States (MS) of the European Union (EU), including their outermost regions.
- [Horizon Europe associated countries](#) (those that have signed an agreement with the EU as identified in the HE Programme Guide) according to the updated list published by the EC.

Additionally, schools must be located in one out of five targeted regions of the SHORE – Open Call #1 - **Baltic Sea, Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Rhine and Danube River Area**:

- [Baltic Sea Area](#)²: Germany, Poland, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Denmark, Sweden, Finland;
- [Black Sea Area](#)³: Romania, Bulgaria, Ukraine, Georgia, Türkiye;

¹ Schools providing up to ISCED level 3, commonly designated as upper secondary education. See a more detailed explanation here: https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/files/Table_III_Qualifications.pdf.

² *Eligible Countries from Baltic Sea Area involve Contracting Parties according to the Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area (Helsinki Convention)*

³ *Eligible Countries from Black Sea Area involve Contracting Parties according to the Bucharest Convention on the Protection of the Black Sea Against Pollution*

- **Mediterranean Sea Area**⁴: Croatia, Cyprus, France, Greece, Italy, Malta, Slovenia, Spain, African countries (Tunisia), Balkan countries (Albania, Montenegro, Bosnia and Herzegovina), Israel, Türkiye;
- **Danube River Area**⁵: Austria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, Germany, Hungary, Moldova, Montenegro, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Ukraine;
- **Rhine River Area**⁶: Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, The Netherlands.

● Figure 2: SHORE - Open Call #1 Target Areas

2.1.3. The European Network of Blue Schools

SHORE – Open Call #1 is open to schools which:

- **are accredited members of the European Network of Blue Schools** at the time of application and provide certificate;
- **aspire to be members of the European Network of Blue Schools and will demonstrate how they intend to meet the prerequisites** to become accredited members by the time of completion of the project.

2.2. Proposal eligibility

- **Each school can submit one application.** At the stage of application, the criteria of time will be applied, as only the last one submitted is going to be taken into consideration, according to the F6S platform information.

⁴ Eligible Countries from Mediterranean Sea Area involve Contracting Parties according to UNEP-MAP (Barcelona Convention)

⁵ Eligible Countries from Danube River Area involve Contracting Parties according to the Danube River Protection Convention (DRPC)

⁶ Eligible Countries from Rhine River Area involve Contracting Parties according to the Convention on the Protection of the Rhine

- **English is the official language for the SHORE - Open Call #1.** Submissions done in any language other than English will not be considered. Applicants should complete all documents in English however proposals will not be judged on writing quality.

2.3. Financial eligibility

- **Each school can benefit from the Financial Support to Third Parties provided under the SHORE project only once.** Schools who receive funding are not eligible to apply in later calls.
- The total budget per project may not exceed **€10,000**. The total amount requested must represent 100% of the total project costs.

2.4. Other conditions

- Applications will not be accepted from entities who are partners or affiliated entities/ linked-third parties in the SHORE consortium or who are formally linked in any way to them.
- Applicants must not have any current and/or potential conflict of interest with the SHORE – Open Call #1 selection process and during the whole project implementation. Applicants must formally and immediately notify the SHORE coordinator of any situation constituting or likely to lead to a conflict of interests and take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation.
- All cases of conflict of interest will be assessed case by case. Applicants must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective evaluation and implementation of the project is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other shared interest ('conflict of interests').
- If a conflict of interest is discovered and confirmed at the time of the evaluation process, the proposal will be considered as non-eligible and will not be evaluated.

3. Proposal preparation and submission

3.1. Proposal preparation

This section describes the relevant requirements for proposals and proposal submission steps.

3.1.1. Which topic should be addressed by the proposal?

The SHORE – Open Call #1 is open to proposals that address at least one topic and subtopic of the open call.

• Figure 3: Topics and subtopics of SHORE – Open Call #1

Applicants should select the most relevant topic and subtopic in line with their proposed activities, the regional context and local environmental challenges. In case more than one topic is relevant, applicants are encouraged to choose the one more suitable for proposed activities.

3.1.2. What kind of activities could be performed during the project?

The SHORE - Open Call #1 is open to proposals which include different types of activities aimed to mobilise primary and secondary schools’ students and/or teachers of the school(s). Applicants are advised to choose at least one activity from a fixed list:

• Table 1: A list of the different types of activities

Activity	Description and examples
workshops	<p>Interactive meetings in which a group of students can meet to discuss questions, brainstorm ideas, identify problems, and develop solutions.</p> <p>Examples of workshops to be led: sustainability action, impacts of climate change, exploring biodiversity, endangered species, sustainable transport, reducing carbon footprint, renewable energy, water conservation, etc.</p>
meetings	<p>gatherings of students that share a common purpose.</p> <p>Examples: presentation the outcomes of the project, etc</p>
trainings	<p>Trainings can be used to develop and embed skills to students, teachers and parents on different issues related to the ocean and water literacy projects. These shall include interactive sessions to</p>

	<p>help learners practise and be effective in their role, supporting lifelong learning.</p> <p>Examples: training on waste management, energy use, pollution, biodiversity, etc.</p>
exhibitions	<p>The aim of an exhibition is to showcase innovative solutions to environmental issues tackled by the blue project and is designed to empower students and visitors to develop their own creative solutions and become advocates for ocean and water literacy.</p> <p>Examples: humorous original drawings, contemporary photographs, artworks made from recycled materials, from litter, fashion shows, etc.</p>
conferences	<p>The purpose of a conference is to provide a platform for students to present their work, talents, and ideas to a wider audience which can include students and teachers from other schools, representatives of local communities, parents, etc.</p> <p>Examples: conferences covering topics related to oceans and rivers, marine science, conservation, education, etc.</p>
meetNtalks	<p>These kinds of meetings aim to provide quality information, advice, and guidance. Students can organise inspiring meetNtalks for presenting the hot topic of their project, create interactive discussions and make use of networking opportunities.</p>
competitions	<p>Competitions are available to students of all ages and come in a slew of different structures and styles.</p> <p>Examples: Students create their own work of art, prose, poetry, or film/photography that interprets a topic as climate heroes, in the wild, recycling, food chain, etc.</p>
virtual educational activities	<p>Virtual educational activities are learning experiences that take place in online or digital environments. They leverage technology to facilitate teaching and engagement, allowing students to access educational content, interact with instructors, and collaborate with peers remotely.</p> <p>Examples: online courses, webinars, virtual field trips, video lectures, interactive simulations, and virtual labs, etc.</p>
field trips	<p>A field trip is one of the tools that can be used to provide every student with real-world experiences. When students leave the</p>

	<p>classroom, they see the connections between what is happening at school and in the 'real-world'.</p> <p>Examples of field trips: to a recycling centre, alternative energy plant, science labs, watch a show with a specific theme related to ocean and water literacy, etc.</p>
local expeditions	<p>These expeditions might be focused on regional and local issues: national parks in the region, botanical gardens, maritime museums, planetarium, zoos or conservation centres, farms, aquariums, fish hatchery, etc.</p>
technical trips	<p>The technical trips are the ones that can be taken to a recycling centre, garbage processing facility, ecological cleanup site, manufacturing plants, science labs, research institutes, etc.</p>
boat activities	<p>These kinds of activities introduce participants to the natural environment of the sea/river, through an educational, on-the-water experience.</p> <p>Examples of activities that can be organised on a boat: observe marine life, bird watching, observe the beach landslides and erosion, etc.</p>
virtual laboratories	<p>Adopting virtual labs represents a step forward in engaging students through active participation. They can be in touch with the latest innovative lab technologies, lab experiments and simulations.</p>
laboratory trips	<p>Laboratory trips to a science laboratory from a research institute/university can substantiate the information received during classes where students can gain hands-on experience and observe scientific experiments or research processes in a real-world condition.</p> <p>Examples: visits to university research labs, government research facilities, industrial research and development centres, and science museums.</p>
museum trips	<p>Museums are great resources and these trips to museums must be truly impactful and lead to a deeper learning. Students should not be just information consumers, but they can play a role in improving the experience and get actively involved by thinking critically. They can look for specific objects, find their story, take photos, create their own exhibition, worksheets, etc.</p>

<p>technical field trips</p>	<p>Technical trips will give real life context to the skills students are learning, build connections between the classroom and the community.</p> <p>Examples: visits to science museums, different environments such as a beach/forest, farms, or just to collect different samples for a project, marine litter monitoring or observation of pollution sources.</p>
<p>laboratory testing and analysis of results</p>	<p>A science lab offers conducting controlled experiments to collect data or samples for analysis. Analysis of results includes the interpretation and evaluation of the data to draw conclusions, make inferences, or generate scientific findings.</p> <p>Examples: testing the composition of a water sample for pollutants, microplastic analysis, etc.</p>

3.1.3. Cooperation/twinning with other blue schools.

SHORE – Open Call #1 welcomes proposals submitted by schools, which are open for collaboration/twinning with other blue schools.

The cooperation can already be established, or schools can intend to establish cooperation during implementation of the project. The cooperation can be established with schools from the Network of European Blue Schools and those aspiring to become accredited members of the Network of European Blue Schools.

In the proposal applicants should describe cooperation activities with other teachers and their students, designed to enable them the exchange of experiences, best practices and successful stories stemming from their blue projects and ocean literacy-driven actions.

Twinning activities aim to promote shared learning among students and teachers with a focus on encouraging learning inside and outside the classroom. Also, teachers can join eTwinning (Community for schools in Europe) to run on-site or online activities with their students along with colleagues from other European countries. Examples of twinning activities include capacity building through knowledge sharing, enabling both partner schools to adopt best practices from each other, twinning visits, etc.

To find suitable partners for cooperation/twinning, please refer to the [EU4Ocean Platform](#) or [eTwinning portal](#).

3.1.4. The European Climate Pact

SHORE – Open Call #1 is open to schools which participate in climate actions and support values of the [European Climate Pact](#). The school’s proposal should entail a commitment to Climate Pact Pledge leading to decarbonisation or at least to carbon neutrality of the project and school activities.

Info on the pledge is here: [European Climate Pact](#) go to take climate friendly action and make a pledge: Take individual action.

Provided justification will be evaluated during the evaluation phase.

3.2. How to submit proposal?

The proposals can be submitted through the F6S platform:

<https://www.f6s.com/shore-open-call-1/apply>

Proposals sent through other methods will be rejected automatically. The applicants are required to **register a profile at F6S** to submit a proposal.

The templates to the Open Call #1 are available on the SHORE website: <https://shoreproject.eu/open-calls-open/>. These are:

- **Annex 2 - SHORE Application Form at F6S:** Includes the administrative questions to be completed directly on the F6S platform: <https://www.f6s.com/shore-open-call-1/apply>. The form is extracted as a document for reference purposes only. The Application form should be directly filled at the F6S platform.
- **Annex 2.1. - SHORE Proposal template:** This describes the project and is structured into multiple mandatory sections document that must be submitted in a pdf format containing the description of the proposed project and uploaded as part of the application form at the F6S platform. Proposal is limited to 11 pages excluding the cover page and ethics and security section.
- **Annex 4 - SHORE Declaration of Honour:** template of the declaration of no conflict of interest and that all conditions related to the SHORE - Open Call #1 are accepted by the applying entity. Upon acceptance of their proposal for funding, the signed and stamped declaration must be submitted.

Applying to an open call takes time and dedication, please make sure you:

- **Be on time:** Make sure you submit your proposal through the F6S platform before the deadline of **20 of March 2024, 17:00 CET**. If you submit the form correctly, the system will send you a confirmation of your submission (please check your SPAM folder as well). Proposals submitted by any other means are ineligible, hence will not be evaluated.
- **Be exhaustive:** Have you answered all the sections of the form and uploaded all required Annexes? It will not be possible to add any information after you submit your application or reach the submission deadline.
- **Every question deserves your attention:** All sections of your proposal must be filled in. Make sure that the data provided is true and complete. This is crucial for us to properly assess your proposal.
- **Documentation format:** Any document requested in any of the phases must be submitted electronically in pdf format without restrictions for printing.

Applicants are recommended to become familiar with **Annex 3** - SHORE Sub-grant agreement and **Annex 4** – SHORE Declaration of Honour. These documents must be provided if the applicant is selected and are mandatory to finalise the contract and enter the implementation phase.

It is strongly recommended to not wait until the last moment of submission. **Failure of the Proposal to arrive in time for any reason, including communications delays, or network issues is not acceptable as an extenuating circumstance and will automatically lead to rejection of the submission.** The time of receipt of the proposal as recorded by the submission system will be definitive.

Please note that after application submission, editing is not possible. If the applicant discovers an error in the proposal and provided the call deadline has not passed, the applicant may request the SHORE - Open Call #1 team to re-submit the proposal (for this purpose please contact us at support@f6s.com with a message titled: RESUBMISSION REQUEST). However, SHORE is not committed that resubmission in time will be feasible in case the request for resubmission is not received by the SHORE team at least 48 hours before the call deadline.

4. How proposals will be evaluated and selected?

This section describes evaluation and selection process of each proposal. The evaluation of proposals is carried out by the SHORE consortium with the support of independent external experts. The SHORE consortium ensures that the process is fair and in line with the principles outlined in the European Commission’s rules on proposal submission and evaluation.

SHORE – Open Call #1 evaluation process will look like as follows on the diagram:

• Figure 4: SHORE – Open Call #1 evaluation process

The proposals will be evaluated by two evaluators according to the criteria shown below.

• Table 2: Evaluation criteria

Criteria	Description	Weight
Relevance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The proposal demonstrates relevance to the implementation of the Mission Ocean objectives, 	40%

C1		<p>as stated in the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters Implementation Plan (section 1.2), and contribution to increasing ocean and water literacy.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The proposal demonstrates a strategy for bringing in a European dimension and cooperation and/or twinning with other schools, in particular with the Network of European Blue Schools. • The proposal entails a commitment to Climate Pact Pledge leading to decarbonisation or at least carbon neutrality of the project and of the proposed school activities. 	
C2	Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The proposal demonstrates the innovative character and the clear output of funded activities. • The proposal demonstrates a strategy for stakeholders and local community engagement in the proposed activities. • The proposal demonstrates how the activities, and the funded project will be promoted locally, nationally or at the European scale. 	30%
C3	Methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The proposal demonstrates a strategy for actively involving students in all phases of project development fostering leadership and co-creation process providing authentic interlinked learning activities through a real-life applicable approach. • The proposal demonstrates a strategy for mobilising more than one classroom of students in the funded activities, including other members of school staff and management. • The proposal demonstrates the existence of a team dedicated to project implementation with educational and management experience related to ocean literacy. The proposal also demonstrates rational project costs. • The proposal demonstrates an open schooling methodology 	30%

4.1. Do you find any shortcoming in evaluation process?

Within three (3) working days of receiving (1) a rejection letter informing the proposal as non-eligible or (2) an ESR of non-acceptance, an applicant may submit a request for redress if they believe the results of the eligibility checks have not been correctly applied, or if they feel that there has been a shortcoming in the way their proposal has been evaluated.

In such a case, an internal review committee from SHORE will examine the applicant's request for a redress. The committee's role is to ensure a coherent interpretation of such requests, and equal treatment of applicants. Requests for redress must:

- Be related to the evaluation process or eligibility checks.

- Clearly describe the complaint (in English).
- Sent by the entity’s legal representative that has also submitted the proposal.

The committee will review the complaint and will recommend an appropriate course of action. If there is clear evidence of a shortcoming that could affect the eventual funding decision, it is possible that all or part of the proposal will be re-evaluated.

Please note:

- This procedure is concerned only with the general evaluation and/or eligibility checking process. The committee will not question the scientific or technical judgement of the evaluators.
- A re-evaluation will only be carried out if there is evidence of a shortcoming that affects the final decision on whether to fund the proposal or not. This means, for example, that a problem relating to one evaluation criterion will not lead to a re-evaluation if a proposal has failed anyway on other criteria.
- The evaluation score following any re-evaluation will be regarded as definitive. It may be lower than the original score.

All requests for redress will be treated in confidence and must be sent to the SHORE team by email to: opencalls@shoreproject.eu

4.2. How the sub-grant agreements will be signed?

After the final project selection, the SHORE consortium will start the contract preparation phase in collaboration with the representatives of the projects that have been awarded. Contract preparation will go via administrative and financial checking (and potentially into technical or ethical/security negotiations) based on evaluators’ comments. On a case-by-case approach, a phone call or teleconference may be needed for clarification.

The objective of the contract preparation is to fulfil the legal requirements between the SHORE consortium and each beneficiary of the open call. The items covered are presented below.

- Table 3: Legal requirements

Requirement	Description
Sub-grant agreement	The contract signed between SHORE Consortium represented by its coordinator (YTU) and the beneficiary. Contract as provided to the sub-grantee is final and may not be changed, including the addition or removal of any articles or other content.
Declaration of Honour	The Document which covers all conditions related to SHORE - Open Call #1 signed by the legal representative of the applying entity.
Bank Account information	The account where the funds will be transferred will be indicated via a specific form signed by the entity,

	Payments will be made in Euro to the bank account indicated by the beneficiary (school).
--	--

The legal representative of the beneficiary will sign the contract and take complete responsibility for executing the proposed activities.

The request of the above listed documentation by the SHORE consortium will be sent to the project representatives, including deadlines by which information and documentation should be sent. In general, the negotiation should be concluded **within 1 month**. An additional period may be provided by the SHORE coordinator in case of a relevant reasoning. In case negotiations have not been concluded within the above period, the proposal is automatically rejected and the next proposal in the reserve list is invited to initiate the contract preparation.

At the end of the contracting phase, the sub-grantee funding agreement will be signed between the SHORE Consortium represented by its coordinator (YTU - YILDIZ TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY) and the selected applicant.

All documentation requires a signature and must be signed with a valid electronic digital signature or by hand (e.g. with the same signature on the identity card).

5. SHORE awarded projects follow-up.

The SHORE consortium will provide support to selected schools to ensure the successful development of their projects. Additionally, SHORE consortium will support schools in applying to the Network of European Blue Schools,

5.1. Implementation, payments and reporting

Selected school projects will last up to **6 months**.

The funds will be disbursed in lump sums in two stages:

- **80% of the grant** will be made available to the awarded schools upon sub-grantee agreement signature,
- **20% of the grant** will be paid upon completion of the project and submission of the final school project report and verification of successful completion of the project.

Reporting

At the end of the project, the selected schools will be required to submit a final report that outlines the activities undertaken in the project, the results achieved, and the lessons learned.

The school project planning and reports will be submitted electronically through the platform mentioned in section 6.5. Country Hubs will assess the quality report and provide feedback to the school.

It is important to mention, that if the activities performed by schools will not be in line with description in proposal or school will not fulfil the obligations set up in sub-grant agreement, EC have a right of recovery regarding any or all the financial support granted under contract.

Detailed information about payments taking into consideration the timeline of each school project will be provided in sub-grant agreement. Schools are advised to get acquainted with the **Annex 3 - SHORE Sub-grant agreement (template)**, which provides a template of the sub-grant agreement that the successful applicants will be requested to sign.

5.2. Country hubs

Project partners acting as SHORE Country Hubs will mentor and guide the schools and students locally about successful Blue Skills Curricula and project implementation. Each targeted region will have country hub as listed below:

- **Baltic Sea region:** Akademia WSB;
- **Black Sea region:** MARE NOSTRUM; Yildiz Technical University; Turk Deniz Arastirmalari Vakfi (TÜDAV);
- **Mediterranean Sea region:** University of Padua; Museo Dei Bambini Societa' Cooperativa Sociale Onlus, Yildiz Technical University;
- **Rhine River region:** Kinderbüro Universität Wien gmbH; Budapest University of Technology and Economics;
- **Danube River region:** Kinderbüro Universität Wien gmbH; Budapest University of Technology and Economics, MARE NOSTRUM.

The Country Hubs will be responsible for supporting the schools locally in targeted regions, including supporting schools in implementation of their projects. Country Hubs will also review the Schools Projects Reports.

Contact details to each country hub can be found on SHORE website: <https://shoreproject.eu/country-hubs/>.

It is expected that the successful applicants organise and run at least one meeting during project implementation with their Country Hub, to present the development of the projects.

5.3. Platform

SHORE consortium will provide to selected schools its own digital platform, which will be a space for schools to enable the follow-up of student and school projects in addition to publishing developed Blue Skills materials for school activities and teacher routes. The platform will serve also as a communication tool with Country Hubs. Each school will create a profile on the platform and provide information about selected projects including its goals, objectives, and performed activities.

5.4. Become the Ocean Ambassador of the year!

After each open call period, an online contest will be held to select the best school projects through a global competition using the SHORE digital platform, and the voting will be open to the public. After the selection of the global winner, the school will be awarded as **“Ocean Ambassador of The Year”** and promoted as such. The label of "SHORE Ocean Literacy

Ambassador School." will be a recognition of the school's commitment to ocean literacy education.

6. Additional considerations

6.1. Data protection

To process and evaluate applications, the SHORE consortium will need to collect Personal and Industrial Data. F6S Network Ireland Limited, will act as Data Controller for data submitted through the F6S platform for these purposes. A Data Protection Officer (DPO) has been appointed by F6S generally, to ensure compliance with data protection regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and that personal data is collected, processed, and stored in a secure manner.

The F6S platform's system design and operational procedures ensure that data is managed in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR). Each applicant will accept the F6S terms to ensure compliance. Please refer to <https://www.f6s.com/privacy-policy> to review the F6S platform's privacy policy and data security policy.

Apart from the F6S platform, data will also be stored in the F6S Google Drive, and in the project repository on Group-Office managed by the project coordinator YILDIZ TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY. Please note that the SHORE consortium must retain generated data until five years after the balance of the SHORE project is paid or longer if there are ongoing procedures (such as audits, investigations or litigation). In this case, the data must be kept until they end.

6.2. Origins of the funds

Selected applicants will sign a dedicated sub-grant funding agreement with the SHORE consortium. The sub-granted funds come directly from the funds of the SHORE project (GA no. 101112815), funded by the European Union within the Horizon Europe Programme.

As detailed in **Annex 3 - SHORE Sub-grant funding agreement template**, this relation between the sub-grantees and the EC through the SHORE project carries a set of obligations to the sub-grantees with the EC. It is the task of the sub-grantees to achieve them and of the SHORE consortium partners to inform about them.

6.3. Promoting the action and giving visibility to the EU funding

The Schools must promote the sub-project by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner and to highlight the financial support of the EU. Detailed requirements are listed in Annex 3 - SHORE Sub-grant Agreement (template).

7. Checklist

- **Does your planned activities fit with the SHORE - Open Call #1?** Check that your proposed activities address one of the objectives of OC # 1.
- **Is your organisation and proposal eligible?** The eligibility criteria are given in section 3. Make sure that you satisfy the minimum project requirements.

- **Budgetary limits.** Check that you comply with any budgetary limits as expressed in section 3.
- **Does your proposal fulfil requested information?** Proposal should be precise, concise, and answer the requested questions designed to correspond to the applied evaluation criteria. Omitting requested information will almost certainly lead to lower scores and possible rejection.
- **Have you submitted your proposal before the deadline?** It is strongly recommended not to wait until the last minute to submit the proposal. Failure of the proposal to arrive in time for any reason, including network communication delays, is not acceptable as an extenuating circumstance. The time of receipt of the message as recorded by the submission system will be definitive.
- **Do you need further advice and support?** You are strongly advised to communicate with the SHORE project team. Please refer to section 9 where you can find all contact information.

8. Do you need more information?

The SHORE consortium will provide information to the applicants primarily via <https://www.f6s.com/shore-open-call-1/apply> so that all information (questions and answers) will be accessible to all potential applicants.

- More info about SHORE at: <https://shoreproject.eu/>
- More information about SHORE – Open Call #1: <https://shoreproject.eu/open-calls/>
- Apply via: <https://www.f6s.com/shore-open-call-1/apply>
- F6S support team (for platform issues during the application): support@f6s.com
- Other support: opencalls@shoreproject.eu

SHORE

Empower students as the agents of change

Funded by the
European Union

SHORE – Open Call #1

Annex 1a - Evaluation and selection

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9. Introduction

This document provides the relevant information regarding evaluation and selection process under Open Call #1 of the SHORE project.

An overview of the SHORE - Open Call #1 can be found in Figure 1.

Figure 5: SHORE - Open Call #1 and follow-up overview

Applications for the SHORE - Open Call #1 will be accepted from **17 January 2024** until **20 March 2024, 17h CET**.

After Open Call closure, there will be a period of evaluation, selection and onboarding which is expected to last for a period of approximately 3 months.

The selected school projects will have an expected duration of up to 6 months (**around 20 beneficiaries selected**).

NOTE: The SHORE project has planned the Open Call #1 and projects follow up in a way to ensure that enough time has been allocated to each school project for successful completion. The SHORE recognizes that unforeseen events might occur. To keep transparency and fairness among applicants of the Open Call, closing dates are fixed dates and will only be updated in case of unforeseen events. All other dates mentioned in this document are tentative and may be updated to accommodate specific needs of the applicant and the consortium.

10. Evaluation process

SHORE – Open Call #1 evaluation process will look like as follows on the diagram:

Figure 6: SHORE – Open Call #1 evaluation process

10.1. How proposals will be evaluated and selected?

This section describes evaluation and selection process of each proposal. The evaluation of proposals is carried out by the SHORE consortium with the support of independent external experts (Evaluation Panel). The SHORE consortium ensures that the process is fair and in line with the principles outlined in the European Commission’s rules on proposal submission and evaluation.

Step 1: Eligibility check

An initial eligibility check will be done by the SHORE team to filter out and discard non-eligible proposals. The following information will be checked:

1. Submission has been made through the F6S platform and by the defined deadline. [Y/N]
2. All the eligibility conditions specified in section 2 are met. [Y/N]
3. The applicant submitted only one proposal [Y/N]
4. The applicant has selected at least one topic and subtopic according to the provided list [Y/N]
5. The proposal, including the F6S application form and all requested and mandatory information and documents, are fully completed (this includes a full technical proposal with all sections completed). [Y/N]
6. The proposal is written in the English Language. [Y/N]

Proposals must meet **ALL the eligibility criteria**. The eligibility check enables the creation of a shortlist of proposals to be evaluated in the next step of the evaluation process.

Proposals marked as non-eligible (for not meeting one or more of the eligibility criteria) will be informed by e-mail.

Step 2: External remote evaluation

Proposals considered eligible will be moved to the remote evaluation phase. The external evaluation will be done remotely by evaluators.

The evaluators will be selected from a pool of experts that will be established through a call for expressions of interest. The call will invite experts to provide their expertise in the domains addressed by the open call, as well as experience in evaluations.

Two external evaluators will evaluate each proposal and will be distributed considering their domains of expertise and, whenever possible, country of origin.

The proposals will be evaluated according to the criteria shown below.

Table 4: Evaluation criteria

Criteria		Description	Weight
C1	Relevance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The proposal demonstrates relevance to the implementation of the Mission Ocean objectives, as stated in the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters Implementation Plan (section 1.2), and contribution to increasing ocean and water literacy. The proposal demonstrates a strategy for bringing in a European dimension and cooperation and/or twinning with other schools, in particular with the Network of European Blue Schools. The proposal entails a commitment to Climate Pact Pledge leading to decarbonisation or at least carbon neutrality of the project and of the proposed school activities. 	40%
C2	Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The proposal demonstrates the innovative character and the clear output of funded activities. The proposal demonstrates a strategy for stakeholders and local community engagement in the proposed activities. The proposal demonstrates how the activities, and the funded project will be promoted locally, nationally or at the European scale. 	30%
C3	Methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The proposal demonstrates a strategy for actively involving students in all phases of project development fostering leadership and co-creation process providing authentic interlinked learning activities through a real-life applicable approach. The proposal demonstrates a strategy for mobilising more than one classroom of students in the funded activities, including other members of school staff and management. The proposal demonstrates the existence of a team dedicated to project implementation with educational and management experience related 	30%

		<p>to ocean literacy. The proposal also demonstrates rational project costs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The proposal demonstrates an open schooling methodology 	
--	--	--	--

Each criterion will be scored between 1 and 5. Half point scores are not given. For each criterion under examination, score values will indicate the following rationale:

Table 5: Results and rationale

Score	Result	Rationale
1	Fail	The proposal fails to address the criterion under examination or cannot be judged due to missing or incomplete information
2	Poor	The criterion is addressed in an unsatisfactory manner. There are serious inherent weakness
3	Good	While the proposal broadly addresses the criterion, there are significant weakness that would need correction
4	Very Good	The proposal addresses the criterion well, although certain improvements are possible
5	Excellent	The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion in question. Any shortcomings are minor.

The score (including for each criterion) is calculated on evaluators consensus reached based on the average of the scores provided by the evaluators, rounded to the nearest point or half point (1, 1.5, 2, 3, 3.5, 4, 4.5, 5), before computing the overall score.

Overall score (after consensus) is the sum of the scores of each criterion multiplied by the respective weight, rounded to the nearest integer value.

The threshold for each criterion is three (3) out of 5 points, therefore any criterion with a lower score is automatically rejected.

$$\text{Overall score} = (C1 * 40 + C2 * 30 + C3 * 30) / 100$$

Each evaluator will record their individual assessment of each proposal using an Individual Evaluation Report (ISR). A single Evaluation Summary Report (ESR) will be prepared by the Evaluation Panel, representing opinions and scores on which the evaluators agree.

Step 3 Consensus meeting

Evaluators involved in the remote evaluation will carry out a consensus meeting with the objective of gathering their evaluations, defining a common score for the proposals, and preparing evaluation reports.

In the end of the evaluation period the consortium will review the scores provided by the different experts to assess the following items:

- I. Significant discrepancies in the scores of specific proposals.
- II. Consistent significant deviations in scoring from specific evaluators.

If any of the deviations are identified, the consortium will hold consensus meetings to consolidate the scores. If significant discrepancies are not resolved, the consortium may request a third evaluator to score the relevant proposals. In the case of adding a third evaluator, the final score of each criterion is computed according to the following formula: $\text{Score} = (\text{lowest score} + \text{medium score} * 4 + \text{highest score}) / 6$

Step 4 Ranking and Final selection

At the end of the remote evaluation process, all proposals will be ranked in a single list.

In case there are proposals with equal scores, tie-breaks will be addressed by giving priority to the proposals with the highest score in specific criteria, considering the following order:

- I. Rule 1: The Applications will be ranked based on their overall score.
- II. Rule 2: In case following Rule 1 there are Applications in the same position, priority will be given to Applications that have higher scores in the criterion I Relevance.
- III. Rule 3: In case following Rule 2 there are Applications in the same position, priority will be given to Applications that have a higher score in the criterion II Impact.
- IV. Rule 4: In case following Rule 3 there are Applications in the same position, priority will be given to the one submitted earliest.

The proposals with higher scores will be selected until reaching the available funding. Around 20 proposals will be selected and invited to the contract negotiation step.

At least 20% of the funded proposals must involve migrants or Ukrainian citizens under temporary protection in funded activities. If needed such proposals will be selected from lower ranked positions to meet this quota.

Every eligible applicant will receive via email:

- An Evaluation Summary Report (ESR);
- A letter informing of the rejection decision or invitation to negotiation and the following steps.

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SHORE – Open Call # 1

Annex 2 – SHORE Application Form

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INSTRUCTIONS

Please note that the question forms provided here are intended for reference purposes only!

In this application form, candidates must submit their school project proposal describing activities aimed at increasing **ocean and water literacy**, among students, teachers and local community by mobilising youth as agents of change while ramping up the accreditation of the Network of European Blue Schools and cross-European collaboration.

The application is divided into the following sections. Failure to provide the required information in all sections will result in disqualification (mandatory fields are marked with *)

This form is available at <https://www.f6s.com/shore-open-call-1/apply>

SHORE Open Call 1 will receive applications from 17 January 2024 at 12:00 PM CET to 20 March 2024 at 5:00 PM CET.

INDIVIDUAL INFO

Full Name*

Please write down a short answer

Email Address *

Please write down a short answer

Your role/position in the school*

Please write down a short answer (multi-line option available)

SCHOOL INFO

Full Name*

Please write down a short answer

Street Address

Please write down a short answer

School website/social media

Please write down a short answer

School info email*

Please write down a short answer

Name of the school's legal representative*

Please write down a short answer

VAT number

Please write down a short answer

School Registration number

Please write down a short answer

Please provide the school's registration number or any official identification that proves its legal status as an educational institution.

ELIGIBILITY

Type of school*

- Elementary school
- Secondary school

Please select a checkbox as your answer

Please specify the age range of students involved in the school's curriculum

Please write down a short answer

Geographical area of the school*

- Baltic Sea Area
- Black Sea Area
- Mediterranean Sea Area
- Danube River Area
- Rhine River Area

Please select a checkbox as your answer

Please state if the school is legally established in one of SHORE Target Areas, according to Annex 1 - SHORE Guidelines for applicants: [click on the PDF link in the online application form](#).

DISCLAIMER: If the school is established in the country which is part of more than one target area (e.g., Austria is eligible both in the Rhine and Danube River Area), the applicant should select the area according to the focus and implementation location of their funded activities.

NOTE: SHORE Open Call 1 is open for schools legally established and based in the European Union or Horizon Associated Countries:

https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/list-3rd-country-participation_horizon- Euratom_en.pdf

If selected Baltic Sea Area, please state the country in which the school is legally established*

- Denmark
- Estonia
- Finland
- Germany
- Latvia
- Lithuania
- Poland
- Sweden

Please select a country from the drop-down list as your answer

NOTE: Eligible Countries from Baltic Sea Area involve Contracting Parties according to the Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area (Helsinki Convention):

<https://helcom.fi/about-us/contracting-parties/>

If selected Black Sea Area, please state the country in which the school is legally established*

- Bulgaria
- Georgia
- Romania
- Ukraine
- G

Please select a country from the drop-down list as your answer

NOTE: Eligible Countries from Black Sea Area involve Contracting Parties according to the Bucharest Convention on the Protection of the Black Sea Against Pollution:

http://www.blacksea-commission.org/_convention.asp

If selected Mediterranean Sea Area, please state the country in which the school is legally established*

- Albania
- Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Croatia
- Cyprus
- Egypt
- France
- Greece
- Italy
- Israel
- Malta
- Montenegro
- Slovenia
- Spain
- Tunisia
- Türkiye

Please select a country from the drop-down list as your answer

NOTE: Eligible Countries from Mediterranean Sea Area involve Contracting Parties according to UNEP-MAP (Barcelona Convention):

https://wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/7096/StatusOfSignaturesAndRatifications_20201029.pdf

If selected Danube River Area, please state the country in which the school is legally established*

Austria
Bosnia and Herzegovina
Bulgaria
Croatia
Czech Republic
Germany
Hungary
Republic of Moldova
Montenegro
Romania
Serbia
Slovakia
Slovenia
Ukraine

Please select a country from the drop-down list as your answer

NOTE: Eligible Countries from Danube River Area involve Contracting Parties according to the Danube River Protection Convention (DRPC): <https://www.icpdr.org/about-icpdr/organisation/contracting-parties#:~:text=The%20Contracting%20Parties%20to%20the,Ukraine%20and%20the%20European%20Union.>

If selected Rhine River Area, please state the country in which the school is legally established*

- Austria
- Belgium
- France
- Germany
- Luxembourg
- The Netherlands

Please select a country from the drop-down list as your answer

NOTE: Eligible Countries from Rhine River Area involve Contracting Parties according to the Convention on the Protection of the Rhine: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A22000A1116%2801%29>

Accreditation in the European Network of Blue Schools*

The applicant is the accredited member of the Network of European Blue Schools

The applicant aspires to become a member of the Network of European Blue Schools and will submit an application to the Network by the time of completion of the SHORE funded project if selected for funding.

Please select a checkbox as your answer

Please state the school's accreditation status in the European Network of Blue Schools, according to Annex 1 - SHORE Guidelines for applicants.

NOTE: the Network of European Blue Schools is established under EU4Ocean coalition: https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/theme/ocean-literacy-and-blue-skills/ocean-literacy/network-blue-schools/become-european-blue-school_en

PROPOSAL INFO

Proposal Acronym*

Please write down a short answer

Please select the topic of your project*

Topic # 1 Sea-based activities

Topic # 2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter

Topic # 3 Biodiversity

Topic # 4 Climate Change

Topic #5 Sustainable use of water resources

Please select a checkbox as your answer (multiple choice available)

The SHORE – Open Call #1 is open to proposals that address at least one topic and subtopic of the open call, according to Annex 1 - SHORE Guidelines for applicants.

If selected Topic # 1, please select related sub-topic of your project

- Fisheries and Aquaculture
- Coastal Tourism
- Marine and River Transport and Shipping
- Biotechnology
- Water Sports

Please select a checkbox as your answer

If selected Topic # 2, please select related sub-topic of your project

- Oil rigs
- Heavy Metals

- Plastics & Microplastics
- Various Wastes from Cruise Ships
- Various Wastes from Cities

Please select a checkbox as your answer

If selected Topic # 3, please select related sub-topic of your project

- Migration of the Species
- Damage to Coral Reefs and Riverbeds
- Microplastics Uptake by Aquatic Animals
- Erosion and Flooding
- Preserve biodiversity in waters

Please select a checkbox as your answer

If selected Topic # 4, please select related sub-topic of your project

- Water-body acidification
- Eutrophication
- Rising Temperature
- Droughts
- Rise in Sea Levels

Please select a checkbox as your answer

If selected Topic # 5, please select related sub-topic of your project

- Renewable Marine and Water Energy
- Nuclear power plants on shores
- Drinking water
- Food from sea and water

Please select a checkbox as your answer

Proposal Template *

Please use File Upload Option on the F6S platform

Please upload a pdf of Proposal Template with all sections filled out, according to Annex 1 - SHORE Guidelines for applicants. Please use Annex 2.1 - SHORE Proposal Template available here: [click on the PDF link in the online application form.](#)

REQUIREMENTS TO JOIN SHORE

If selected, do you agree to sign the “Annex 4 - SHORE Declaration of Honour”

Yes

No

Please select a checkbox as your answer

I CONFIRM that I accept all conditions in ANNEX 4 - SHORE Declaration of Honour and information contained therein and that it will be provided signed and stamped if this proposal will be accepted for funding. Click here to visualise this document: [click on the PDF link in the online application form](#).

Acceptance of the SHORE Open Call rules*

- Yes, I have reviewed and accepted all the conditions of Annex 1 - SHORE Guidelines for applicants

Please select a checkbox as your answer

Click here to visualise the Annex 1 - SHORE Guidelines for applicants available at: [click on the PDF link in the online application form](#).

Agree on GDPR*

- Yes, I accept

Please select a checkbox as your answer

Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679>

Double Funding*

- No risk of double funding

Please select a checkbox as your answer

Proposals from applicants and linked schools (see table of Terms and Definitions) must demonstrate that there is no risk of double funding. The fundamental principle underpinning the rules for public expenditure in the EU states that no costs for the same activity can be funded twice from the EU budget, as defined in the Article 111 of Council Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 1605/2002 of 25 June 2002 on the Financial Regulation.

Conflict of Interest*

- To the best of our knowledge, there is no conflict of interest

Please select a checkbox as your answer

Beneficiaries must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the sub-project is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other shared interest.

OTHER

How did you find out about this call?

Social Media

- Please let us know which social media (and which profile, if possible)

Referrals from other EU projects

- Please let us know which EU project, if possible

European Commission Communications

- Please let us know which European Commission Communications, if possible

F6S website

SHORE Consortium

- Please let us know which project partner from the SHORE consortium, if possible

Search Engine

- Please let us know which Search Engine, if possible

Event

- Please let us know which event, is possible

Other

- Please let us know which other channel or contact, is possible

Please select a checkbox as your answer. Depending on your choice, different sub-question will appear (please write down a short answer)

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SHORE – Open Call # 1

Annex 2.1 – SHORE Proposal Template

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INSTRUCTIONS

- Please use this template to prepare your proposal. It has been organised to ensure that the important aspects of your proposal are clearly measurable with respect to the evaluation criteria.
- The page limit for the proposal (section 1-4) is **11 pages** (not including cover page and the Ethical/Security Checklist). All tables, figures, references and any other element pertaining to these sections must be included as an integral part of these sections.
- Recommended font type is “**Calibri**” and the minimum **font size is 11 points**.
- It is mandatory to save the document in PDF before uploading.
- **If you attempt to upload a proposal longer than the specified limit, your proposal may not be taken into consideration by the evaluators. Any pages over the 11-page limit won't be taken into consideration by the evaluators.**
- **ENGLISH is the only eligible language of the proposal.**

Please be aware that the proposal will be evaluated as it was submitted, with no additional documents or links to add information beyond the defined hereby. The proposal is a self-contained document. **Evaluators will be instructed to ignore hyperlinks to information that is specifically designed to expand the proposal, thus circumventing the page limit.**

Please delete this page and the previous SHORE cover page before submitting the proposal. Your proposal should start with the PROPOSAL COVER PAGE (next page). Delete the information text in each section and any template footnotes.

PROPOSAL COVER PAGE

PROPOSAL INFORMATION	
Acronym of your proposal:	
Title of proposal:	
School info (name) details	
School VAT	
School Registration Number	
Country	
Date of submission	

1. SUMMARY OF YOUR PROPOSAL

NOTE: maximum 0,5 page

Please provide a summary of your project that can be published if the project will be selected for funding.

2. RELEVANCE

NOTE: max 3 pages

2.1 Please describe how your proposal is aligned with the Mission Ocean objectives, and how you plan to contribute to increasing ocean and water literacy.

2.2 Please describe the strategy for bringing in a European dimension to the project and describe potential cooperation/twinning with other blue schools. Please explain how the cooperation will be implemented, what will be the objectives and main activities undertaken.

2.3 Please explain if and how the project activities will have a positive impact on the environment. Please describe schools' commitment to Climate Pact Pledge leading to decarbonisation or at least to carbon neutrality of the project and school activities and if the school supports the values of a [European Climate Pact](#).

2.4. If you aspire to be a member of the European Network of Blue Schools please describe how you intend to meet the prerequisites to become accredited members by the time of completion of the project.

3. IMPACT

NOTE: max 3 pages

3.1 Project partners are crucial for the success of the project. Please describe planned strategy for stakeholders and local community engagement in the activities which will be performed during project implementation. Please be specific and mention who and which organisation on the local level is crucial for the project implementation and how you plan to reach them.

3.2 Please describe what makes your project and funded activities innovative.

3.3 Please describe how the project will be promoted locally, nationally or at the European scale.

4. METHODOLOGY

NOTE: max 4 pages

4.1 Please choose which activities will be performed during project implementation:

Activity		Activity	
workshops	<input type="checkbox"/>	virtual laboratories	<input type="checkbox"/>
meetings	<input type="checkbox"/>	laboratory trips	<input type="checkbox"/>
trainings	<input type="checkbox"/>	museum trips	<input type="checkbox"/>
exhibitions	<input type="checkbox"/>	technical field trips	<input type="checkbox"/>
conferences	<input type="checkbox"/>	technical trips	<input type="checkbox"/>
meetNtalks	<input type="checkbox"/>	field trips	<input type="checkbox"/>
Competitions	<input type="checkbox"/>	local expeditions	<input type="checkbox"/>
laboratory testing and analysis of results	<input type="checkbox"/>	boat activities	<input type="checkbox"/>
virtual educational activities	<input type="checkbox"/>		

4.2 Please describe chosen activities and planned results including an open schooling methodology. Please be specific about the results and indicate how many students and/or teachers will be involved and how many events will be implemented during school project:

Activity name	Description	Planned outputs	Planned duration

4.3 Please describe how the project involves activities with authentic learning experience for students through a real-life applicable approach in classroom conditions.

4.4 Please describe how project development and implementation plan involve students during the whole lifespan of the project and how the co-creation process and leadership will be fostered among all students.

4.5 Please describe the strategy for involving more than one classroom of students in the funded activities, including other members of school staff and management. Additionally, if you plan to involve migrants or Ukrainian citizens under temporary protection please mention it in the description.

4.6 Please summarise the expected project costs in the table below.

Cost category	Total	Description
[A] Personnel costs		
[B] Travel costs		
[C] Equipment costs		
TOTAL PROJECT COSTS	xxx	

4.7 Please summarise the competencies of the team involved in the proposal in the table below.

Name of the Person	Role in the proposal	Competences

ANNEX: ETHICS & SECURITY Self-Assessment

Ethics/ Security Checklist to be completed.

Must check only if the activities go beyond normal school and school related activities, and are not included in school rules.

		YES / NO
Informed consent		
Does the proposal involve children?		
Does the proposal involve patients or persons not able to give consent?		
Does the proposal involve adult healthy volunteers?		
Does the proposal involve Human Genetic Material?		
Does the proposal involve Human biological samples?		
Does the proposal involve Human data collection?		
Research on human embryo/foetus		
Does the proposal involve Human Embryos?		
Does the proposal involve Human Foetal Tissue / Cells?		
Does the proposal involve Human Embryonic Stem Cells?		
Privacy		
Does the proposal involve processing of genetic information or personal data (e.g., health, sexual lifestyle, ethnicity, political opinion, religious or philosophical conviction)		
Does the proposal involve tracking the location or observation of people?		
Research on animals		
Does the proposal involve research on animals?		
Are those animals transgenic small laboratory animals?		
Are those animals transgenic farm animals?		
Are those animals cloned farm animals?		
Are those animals nonhuman primates?		
Research involving developing countries		
Use of local resources (genetic, animal, plant etc)		
Benefit to local community (capacity building i.e., access to healthcare, education etc)		

Dual use	
Research having direct military application	
Research having the potential for terrorist abuse	
ICT implants	
Does the proposal involve clinical trials of ICT implants?	
I CONFIRM THAT NONE OF THE ABOVE ISSUES APPLY TO MY PROPOSAL	

Ethics

If you have entered any ethics issues in the Ethics/ Security checklist, you must:

- Submit an ethics self-assessment, which:
 - Provides a rationale for the option made.
 - Describes how the proposal meets the national legal and ethical requirements of the country or countries where the tasks raising ethical issues are to be carried out.
 - Explains in detail how you intend to address the issues in the ethical issues table, as regards:
 - Research objectives (e.g., study of vulnerable populations, dual use, etc.).
 - Research methodology (e.g., clinical trials, involvement of children and related consent procedures, protection of any data collected, etc.).
 - The potential impact of the research (e.g., dual use issues, environmental damage, stigmatisation of particular social groups, political or financial retaliation, benefit-sharing, malevolent use, etc.).
- Provide the documents that you need under national law (if you already have them), e.g.:
 - An ethics committee opinion.
 - The document notifying activities raising ethical issues or authorising such activities.

 If these documents are not in English, you must also submit an English summary of them (containing, if available, the conclusions of the committee or authority concerned).

 If you plan to request these documents specifically for the project you are proposing, your request must contain an explicit reference to the project title.

Security

Please indicate if your project will involve:

- Activities or results raising security issues: _____ [YES/NO]
- 'EU-classified information' as background or results: _____ [YES/NO]
- Any potential "dual use" of results: _____ [YES/NO]

Please provide explanation for mentioned above ethics self-assessment here:

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SHORE – Open Call #1

Annex 3 – SHORE Sub-grant agreement template

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Contracting parties

This **Agreement** ('the Agreement') is **between** the following parties:

On the one part,

Yildiz Technical University established in Davutpaşa Campus: Davutpaşa Mah. Davutpaşa Caddesi 34220, Esenler / İstanbul, TÜRKİYE, VAT number TR9650041985 represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by Prof.Dr. Afşin ÇETİNKAYA, acting as Coordinator of the SHORE consortium.

Hereinafter referred to as the “Coordinator”,

And, on the other part,

[Redacted] [Organisation name/ Individual name]
established in [Redacted], [Full Official address], VAT
number [Redacted], represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by
[Redacted] [Name of legal representative],

Hereinafter referred to as the “Beneficiary”.

Hereinafter, all parties above are collectively referred to as the “Contracting Parties”

The Contracting Parties **HAVE AGREED** to the following terms and conditions including those in the following Annexes, which form an integral part of this Sub-Grant Agreement (hereinafter referred as the “Contract”).

General Provisions

The European Commission (hereinafter referred as the “EC”) and the Coordinator, as partner and representative of the SHORE consortium, have signed the Grant Agreement no. 101112815 for the implementation of the SHORE project – SHORE: EmpOweR Students as the agents of cHange – within the framework of the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, HORIZON-MISS-2022-OCEAN-01-08.

The SHORE project is implemented by the Coordinator, as coordinator of the SHORE project, in collaboration with the other SHORE partners. The SHORE consortium partners have among themselves entered into a written agreement detailing their respective rights and obligations towards each other for carrying out the SHORE project and exploiting the results thereof (“the Consortium Agreement” or “CA”).

The objective of SHORE is to focus on engaging & mobilising students, teachers, and schools to implement the Mission Ocean objectives to increase ocean literacy with the help of community activities & cooperation projects. The SHORE project lasts for 36 months and covers five different regional areas (Baltic, Black, Mediterranean Sea, Danube & Rhine River Area) with its 14 consortium partners. SHORE will provide grants to 100 schools through three open calls to support blue projects for a maximum amount of up to 10.000 euro per grant. Educational materials and training for educators will be available during the project to increase their knowledge about sustainable and blue education. A digital platform will be set-up to monitor school projects and provide a virtual learning environment system including rewards and badges. In addition, at the end of each school period, a public voting session will be held to raise awareness & engagement, create a wider audience and select the best school project which will receive an Award.

The Beneficiary has been selected for funding under the SHORE – OPEN CALL #1 based on the positive evaluation of external evaluators.

This Contract aims at defining the framework of rights and obligations of the Contracting Parties with respect to the Beneficiary’s participation in the SHORE – OPEN CALL #1.

The funding to be received by the Beneficiary is property of the EC. The Coordinator is the sole holder and manager of the funds.

Article 1 - Entry into force and termination of the contract

1.1. Entry into force

This Contract will enter into force on the day of its signature by the last Contracting Party. The Coordinator will sign this contract only after all the following documents have been received from the Beneficiary:

- The original signed Declaration of Honour (as provided in Annex 4).
- Bank Account Information form (as provided in Annex 5).

The Beneficiary is solely responsible for the accuracy of all data provided.

The contact details of the Beneficiary for notices and communication under this contract are:

Name of contact person	
Address	
E-mail	
Telephone/ mobile phone	

1.2. Contract termination

This Contract will automatically terminate at the end of SHORE – Open Call #1 Programme, which will happen when the Beneficiary has fulfilled all obligations in Article 2, except for those obligations that according to their content are intended to remain in effect, which keep their full force and effect (e.g., reporting on exploitation activities).

The Coordinator shall be entitled to terminate this Contract by written notice with immediate effect if the Beneficiary does not fulfil its obligations (see Article 3 - Breach of Contractual obligations).

Irrespective of the automatic termination of this Contract under present Article 1.2 or any early termination under Article 4, all obligations that according to their content are intended to be in effect for longer shall remain in effect.

Article 2 - Obligations and responsibilities of the Beneficiary

The obligations and responsibilities are defined in detail in Annex 1 – SHORE Guidelines for Applicants.

Additionally, the Beneficiary shall take every necessary precaution to avoid any risk of conflict of interest relating to economic interests, political or national affinities, personal or any other interests liable to influence the impartial and objective performance of the sub-project. In case the Beneficiary is involved in a conflict of interest or in a risk of conflict of interest, the Beneficiary must formally notify this situation to the Coordinator without delay and immediately take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation.

Furthermore, the Beneficiary shall provide true and accurate documentation and declarations as defined in Article 1.1.

Article 3 - Breach of contractual obligations

In the event of a breach of the contractual obligation's representations or warranties by the Beneficiary under this Contract, the Coordinator, in coordination with the SHORE Consortium, reserves the right to terminate the Contract by written notice with immediate effect, even if such non-fulfilment is due to Force Majeure.

In the event of the breach of the contractual obligations by the Beneficiary, Coordinator reserves the right of not fulfilling the respective payment to the Beneficiary.

The Coordinator also reserves the right to claim a refund of any already paid funds, both in case of breach of contract and/or in case the work/costs are not approved by the EC.

The Coordinator will give written notice requiring that such breach to be remedied within 30 days.

In case the Beneficiary has not brought remedies from the notice, the Coordinator may decide to terminate the contract unilaterally.

Article 4 – Financial contribution and financial provisions

4.1 Maximum financial contribution

The maximum financial contribution to be granted to the Beneficiary shall not exceed the amount of **xxx EUR (xxx.xxx,00)**. This financial contribution will be given in 2 instalments.

4.2 Distribution of the financial contribution

The financial contribution to be granted to the Beneficiary will be calculated and distributed in accordance with the provisions set in Annex 1 – SHORE Guidelines for Applicants.

The financial grant to be paid will always be subject to:

- Provision of a final report and a favourable review by the SHORE internal evaluation team responsible for assessing the sub-project.

Note: A non-favourable review of the work carried out at the end of the sub-project may lead to the early termination of the contract and suspension of payments.

- The prior notice to the Beneficiary of the date and amount to be transferred to its bank account (Annex 5 - Bank account information form), providing the relevant references.
- Payments to the Beneficiary will be made by the Coordinator. In particular:
 - The Coordinator reserves the right to withhold the payments in case the Beneficiary does not fulfil its obligations and tasks as per Annex 1 – SHORE Guidelines for Applicants.
 - Banking and transaction costs related to the handling of any financial resources made available to the Beneficiary will be covered by the Beneficiary.
 - Payments will be released no later than thirty (30) calendar days after the notification by the Coordinator to the Beneficiary that the deliverables and reports have been approved.

The Beneficiary is responsible for complying with any tax and legal obligations that might be attached to this Contract.

4.3 Payments schedule

The payment schedule is directly linked to the relevant stages of the sub-project according to Annex 1 – SHORE Guidelines for Applicants. The first payment will be disbursed automatically after signing the sub-grant agreement. The final payment will be disbursed once all work has received positive assessment, supported on the final report submitted to the SHORE team.

The financial contribution will be made to the Beneficiary by the Coordinator. During the contractual procedure, the Beneficiary will be asked to provide the respective bank account information to which the payments will be made (as provided in Annex 5).

The Beneficiary should submit to the SHORE consortium final report no later than ten (10) calendar days after the end of the project, providing sufficient time for the SHORE consortium to review it. A review will be held between fifteen (15) to thirty (30) calendar days after submitting the final report so that the Contracting Parties can present their work (as reported in the respective report) and provide answers to questions from the mentors and SHORE consortium.

The payments will be made to the Beneficiary subject to the receipt of an invoice or a filled out Financial Identification Form (FIF) and/ or Payment Request Form. If the Beneficiary chooses to send an invoice, the invoice must include the following information:

- Project xxx – Grant no. xxx
- SHORE – OPEN CALL #1
- The Stage to which the payment is associated (e.g. Stage xx)
- Beneficiary information (e.g. sub-project acronym and beneficiary name)

The invoice or the FIF is to be sent to e-mail: xxx. Payments will be made no later than thirty (30) calendar days after receipt of the invoice or FIF to the bank account of the Beneficiary. All payments will be made in Euros.

NOTE: If at final payment stage the SHORE team considers that the quality of work demonstrated and/or reported does not correspond to what has been agreed, the two parties may agree to a respective reassessment. If significant improvements are not delivered after the reassessment and the sub-project is therefore considered to be in breach of their contractual obligations, SHORE reserves the right to terminate the contract as outlined in *Article 3 – Breach of contractual obligations*.

Article 5 - Liability

5.1 Liability of the Beneficiary

The Beneficiary shall fully and exclusively bear the risks in connection with the fulfilment of its tasks and obligations under this Contract. Except in case of force majeure (Article 8), the Beneficiary must compensate the Coordinator and the EC for any damage they sustain because of the implementation of the obligations of the Beneficiary under this Contract or because the tasks and obligations of the Beneficiary were not implemented in full compliance with this Contract.

Accordingly, neither SHORE Consortium nor the EC can be held liable for any damage caused to the Beneficiary or to third parties because of implementing this Contract, including for gross negligence. At the same time, neither SHORE consortium nor the EC can be held liable for any damage caused by the Beneficiary or third parties, because of implementing this Contract.

The Beneficiary shall bear sole responsibility for ensuring that its acts within the framework of this Contract do not infringe third parties' rights. There is no joint liability between the Contracting Parties.

For this purpose, the Beneficiary shall indemnify and hold the Coordinator and the EC harmless from and against all repayments, loss, liability, costs, charges, claims or damages which the Coordinator or the EC as a result thereof would incur or suffer or must pay to the EC or any third parties. In addition, should the EC have a right of recovery against SHORE consortium regarding any or all the financial support granted under this Contract, the Beneficiary shall repay the sums in question in the terms and on the date specified by the Coordinator.

5.2 Exclusions of liability

To the extent acceptable under applicable law, in no event shall the Coordinator or other SHORE consortium partners be liable to the Beneficiary for loss or damage caused by the Coordinator or the SHORE consortium partners, their employees, agents and subcontractors in connection with this Contract for any of the following, however caused or arising, on any theory of liability, and even if the Coordinator and/or any other SHORE consortium partner were informed or aware of the possibility thereof:

- Loss of profits, revenue, income, interest, savings, shelf-space, production, and business.
- Opportunities; lost contracts, goodwill, and anticipated savings.
- Loss of or damage to reputation or to data.
- Costs of recall of products.
- Any type of indirect, incidental, punitive, special, or consequential loss or damage.

In respect of any information or materials from the SHORE consortium made available to the Beneficiary under this Contract, no warranty or representation of any kind is made, given, or implied as to the sufficiency, error-free performance, or fitness for purpose, nor as to the absence of any infringement of any proprietary rights of third parties. Therefore, in particular, but without limiting the foregoing:

- The Beneficiary shall in all cases be entirely and solely liable for the use to which it puts such information and materials, and the consequences of such use, and
- Neither the Coordinator, the EC nor the other SHORE consortium partners shall be liable vis-à-vis the Beneficiary in case of infringement of proprietary rights of a third party resulting from the Beneficiary's use of the information and material.

The exclusions and limitations stated in this Article and any other clause of this Contract that has as its object or effect the exclusion or limitation of liability, shall not apply in respect of any: fraud; death, injury to natural persons or damage to real or immovable property caused by the negligence or wilful act, wilful misconduct, wilful breach; or otherwise in so far as mandatory applicable law overrides such exclusions and limitations.

Article 6 - Confidentiality

6.1 Principles

Regarding all information of whatever nature or form as is disclosed between the Contracting Parties in connection with the Sub-project and identified in writing as confidential, the terms of this Article shall apply.

6.2 Obligations

All information, in whatever form or mode of communication, which is disclosed by a Contracting Party (the "Disclosing Party") to the other Contracting Party (the "Recipient") in connection with the implementation of the SHORE – OPEN CALL #1 and which has been explicitly marked as "confidential" at the time of disclosure, or, when disclosed orally, has been identified as confidential at the time of disclosure and has been confirmed and designated in writing within 15 calendar days from oral disclosure (at the latest) as confidential information by the Disclosing Party, is "Confidential Information".

The Recipient hereby accepts, in addition and without prejudice to any commitment on nondisclosure towards the EC, for a period of 5 (five) years after the end of the Contract:

- Not to use Confidential Information other than for the purpose for which it was disclosed.
- Not to disclose Confidential Information without the prior written consent by the Disclosing Party.
- To ensure that internal distribution of Confidential Information by a Recipient shall take place on a strict need-to-know basis.
- To return to the Disclosing Party, or destroy, on demand, all Confidential Information that has been disclosed to the Recipient, including all copies and to delete all information stored in a machine-readable form to the extent practically possible. The Recipient may keep a copy to the extent it is required to keep, archive, or store such Confidential Information because of compliance with applicable laws and regulations or for the proof of on-going obligations provided that the Recipient complies with the confidentiality obligations herein contained with respect to such copy for as long as the copy is retained.

The Recipient shall be responsible for the fulfilment of the above obligations on the part of their employees or third parties involved in the implementation of SHORE – OPEN CALL #1 and shall ensure that they remain so obliged, as far as legally possible, during and after the end hereof and/or after the termination of the contractual relationship with the employee or third party. The Recipient shall apply the same degree of care regarding the Confidential Information disclosed within the scope of the project as with its own confidential and/or proprietary information, but in no case less than reasonable care. Each Contracting Party shall promptly advise the other Contracting Party in writing of any unauthorised disclosure, misappropriation, or misuse of Confidential Information after it becomes aware of such unauthorised disclosure, misappropriation, or misuse.

6.3 Exceptions to the obligation of confidentiality

The information above (Article 6.2) shall not apply for disclosure or use of Confidential Information, if and in so far as the Recipient can show that:

- The Confidential Information has become or becomes publicly available by means other than a breach of the Recipient's confidentiality obligations.
- The Disclosing Party subsequently informs the Recipient that the Confidential Information is no longer confidential.
- The Confidential Information is communicated to the Recipient without any obligation of confidentiality by a third party who is to the best knowledge of the Recipient in lawful possession thereof and under no obligation of confidentiality to the Disclosing Party.
- The disclosure or communication of the Confidential Information is foreseen by provisions of the Grant Agreement.
- The Confidential Information, at any time, was developed by the Recipient completely independently of any such disclosure by the Disclosing Party.
- The Confidential Information was already known to the Recipient prior to disclosure.
- Disclosure of the Confidential Information follows mandatory applicable laws or regulations or with a court or administrative order.

6.4 Authorised disclosure(s)

If any Party becomes aware that it will be required, or is likely to be required, to disclose Confidential Information to comply with applicable laws or regulations or with a court or administrative order, it will,

to the extent it is lawfully able to do so under the laws and legislation applicable to said Party, prior to any such disclosure:

- Notify the Disclosing Party, and
- Comply with the Disclosing Party's reasonable instructions to protect the confidentiality of the information.

The SHORE Coordinator's disclosure of Confidential Information to the EC and/or the other SHORE consortium partners shall be governed exclusively by the terms of the Grant Agreement and/or the Consortium Agreement.

Accordingly, nothing in this Contract shall prevent the SHORE Coordinator from complying with its obligations, including its reporting obligations, towards the EC and the other SHORE consortium partners, and any such disclosures shall be subject to the terms of the Grant Agreement or Consortium Agreement.

Likewise, the Beneficiary agrees and acknowledges that the EC shall be entitled to disclose Confidential Information to its staff, other EU institutions and bodies or third parties, if:

- This is necessary to implement the Grant Agreement or safeguard the EU's financial interests.
- The recipients of the information are bound by an obligation of confidentiality.

Article 7 - Intellectual property rights

The Beneficiary acknowledges that all tools, modules and similar of the SHORE partners are proprietary and owned by the respective SHORE partner or applicable third party.

Nothing in this Contract shall transfer to the Beneficiary or other partners it represents any licence or other rights for the use of the tools, modules and similar that are property of an SHORE partner, unless a specific agreement is established.

The results developed during the sub-project shall be exclusively the property of the Beneficiary. This does not exclude the possibility for specific agreements to be made between the Beneficiary and one or more of the partners of SHORE.

Article 8 - Force Majeure

"Force Majeure" means any unforeseeable exceptional situation or event beyond the Contracting Parties control, which prevents either of them from fulfilling any of their obligations under the Agreement, which was not attributable to error or negligence on their part and which proves to be inevitable despite the exercising of all due diligence.

Any default of a service, defect in equipment or material or delays in making them available, unless they stem directly from a relevant case of force majeure, as well as labour disputes, strikes or financial difficulties cannot be invoked as Force Majeure.

The Contracting Parties shall take the necessary measures to limit any damage due to Force Majeure. They shall do their best to resume the implementation of the action as soon as possible.

No Contracting Party shall be in breach of its obligations and tasks if such a breach is caused by Force Majeure. A Contracting Party will notify the other Contracting Party of any Force Majeure as soon as possible. In case the Beneficiary is not able to overcome the consequences of Force Majeure within thirty

calendar (30) days after such notification, the SHORE Coordinator will decide accordingly, including the termination of the Contract.

Article 9 - Information and communication

9.1 Information and communication towards the EC

The Beneficiary shall, throughout the duration of the sub-project, take appropriate measures to engage with the public and the media about the sub-project and **to highlight the financial support of the EC and the SHORE project.**

Unless the EC requests otherwise, any publicity, including at a conference or seminar or any type of information or promotional material (brochure, leaflet, poster, presentation etc.), and any infrastructure, equipment, and major results must:

- Specify that the sub-project has received research funding from the EC through the SHORE project.
- Display the European emblem along with the SHORE logo. When displayed in association with a logo, the European emblem should be given appropriate prominence. This obligation to use the European emblem in respect of projects to which the EC contributes implies no right of exclusive use. It is subject to general third-party use restrictions which do not permit the appropriation of the emblem, or of any similar trademark or logo, whether by registration or by any other means. Under these conditions, the Beneficiary is exempt from the obligation to obtain prior permission from the EC to use the emblem.
- Specify that it reflects only the author's views and that the EC and the SHORE Consortium is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The following text should be used:

"The [sub-project acronym] has indirectly received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation action programme, via the SHORE – Open Call #1 issued and executed under the SHORE project (Grant Agreement no. 101112815)."

The Coordinator, the SHORE consortium, and/or the EC shall be authorised to publish, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, the following information:

- The name of the Beneficiary.
- Contact address of the Beneficiary.
- The general purpose of the sub-project (publishable summary, etc.)
- The amount of the financial contribution of the EC foreseen for the sub-project. after the final payment, the amount and rate of the financial contribution of the EC accepted by the EC.
- The estimated amount and rate of the financial contribution of the EC foreseen for the Beneficiary in the table of the estimated breakdown of budget.
- The geographic location of the activities carried out.
- The list of dissemination activities and/or of patent (applications) relating to foreground.
- The publishable reports submitted (technical reports are excluded, since they are confidential).
- Any picture or any audio-visual or web material provided to the EC in the framework of the Sub-project.

The Beneficiary shall ensure that all necessary authorisations for such publication have been obtained and that the publication of the information by the SHORE Coordinator, the SHORE consortium partners, or EC does not infringe any rights of third parties.

Upon a duly supported request by the Coordinator on behalf of the Beneficiary, the EC may agree to forego such publicity if disclosure of the information indicated above would risk compromising the beneficiary's security, academic or commercial interests.

9.2 Information and communication among the Contracting Parties

Any notice to be given under this Contract shall be in writing to the addresses and recipients listed above. Any change of persons or contact details shall be notified immediately to the SHORE Coordinator. The address list shall be made accessible to all parties concerned.

Article 10 - Checks and reviews

The EC may, at any time during the implementation of the sub-project and up to five years after the end of the sub-project, arrange for a check and review to be carried out, by external auditors, or by the EC services themselves, including the European Anti-Fraud office (OLAF). The procedure shall be deemed to be initiated on the date of receipt of the relevant letter sent by the EC.

There will be no financial checks, reviews, or audits to check costs, since beneficiaries have no obligation to document the costs incurred for the action. Checks, reviews, and audits will focus on the technical implementation of the action.

The Beneficiary shall make available directly to the EC all information and data that may be requested by the EC or any representative authorised by it, in view of verifying that the Grant Agreement is properly managed and performed in accordance with its provisions.

The Beneficiary shall keep the originals or, in exceptional cases, duly authenticated copies (including electronic copies) of all documents related to the Grant Agreement for up to five years from the end of the sub-project. These shall be made available to the EC when requested during any check under the Grant Agreement.

To carry out these checks, the Beneficiary shall ensure that the EC's services and any external body(ies) authorised by it have on-the-spot access at all reasonable times, notably to the Beneficiary's offices, to its computer data, and to all the information needed to carry out those checks. They shall ensure that the information is readily available on the spot during an audit and, if so requested, that data be handed over in an appropriate form.

Based on the findings made during the check, a provisional report shall be drawn up. It shall be sent by the EC or its authorised representative to the Beneficiary concerned, which may make observations thereon within one month of receiving it. The EC may decide not to take into account observations conveyed or documents sent after that deadline. The final report shall be sent to the Beneficiary concerned within two months of expiry of the aforesaid deadline.

Based on the conclusions of the check, the EC shall take all appropriate measures which it considers necessary, including the issuing of recovery orders regarding all or part of the payments made by it and the application of any applicable sanction.

The European Court of Auditors shall have the same rights as the EC, notably right of access, for the purpose of checks and audits, without prejudice to its own rules.

In addition, the EC may carry out on-the-spot checks and inspections in accordance with Council Regulation (Euratom, EC) No 2185/96 of 11 November 1996 concerning on-the-spot checks and inspections carried out by the EC to protect the European Communities' financial interests against fraud and other irregularities.

Article 11 – Data protection

The Contracting Parties have the obligation to abide by the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation – GDPR) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

Each Contracting Party shall each be considered a separate and independent data controller, as defined in the GDPR, to every other Contracting Party. The processing of personal data shall be carried out lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner, collected for specific purposes and adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which it is processed. Where it might be designated by a relevant Supervisory Authority or through agreement between Contracting Parties that the SHORE Coordinator and any other SHORE consortium partners are appointed as data processors, parties shall enter into appropriate data processing agreements as required by the GDPR.

The Beneficiary acknowledges that the SHORE Coordinator and any other SHORE consortium partners, if appointed as data processors, are not responsible for the Beneficiary's compliance with any data protection or privacy law applicable to the Beneficiary. Each of the Contracting Parties, in their respective roles as data controllers, will be responsible for their own compliance with any data protection or privacy law applicable to them as data controller.

Article 12 - Obligations imposed by the Grant Agreement to the Beneficiary

The Beneficiary receives funding from the European Commission for carrying out the sub-project [redacted] [sub-project acronym]. Under the Grant Agreement or the Consortium Agreement, some of the obligations must be imposed on the Beneficiary. Those obligations are reflected in this Agreement. The specific obligations that the Beneficiaries must ensure are described in the Annotated Model Grant Agreement (AGA) for Horizon Europe.⁷ Some of these articles are included in this Contract and are fully applicable to the Beneficiary.

Article 13 - Miscellaneous

Should any provision of this Contract be or become invalid, illegal, or unenforceable, it shall not affect the validity of the remaining provisions of this Contract. In such a case, the Contracting Parties shall be entitled to request that a valid, legal, enforceable, and practicable replacement provision be negotiated which fulfils the purpose of the original provision.

The Beneficiary shall not be entitled to act or to make legally binding declarations on behalf of the Coordinator or any other SHORE consortium partner, and nothing in this Contract shall be deemed to constitute a joint venture, agency, partnership, interest grouping or any other kind of formal business grouping or entity between the Contracting Parties or between the Beneficiary and any SHORE consortium partner.

No rights or obligations of the Beneficiary arising from this Contract may be assigned or transferred, in whole or in part, and no obligations of the Beneficiary may be sub-contracted, without the Coordinator's

⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf

prior formal written approval; and such approval shall not exempt the Beneficiary from any of its obligations hereunder.

Although (with exception to the Coordinator) the SHORE consortium partners and their affiliated entities are not Contracting Parties to this Contract, they are intended by the Contracting Parties to be third party beneficiaries under this Contract and accordingly shall be entitled to enforce the terms of this Contract against the Beneficiary and (without limitation) shall be entitled to the benefit of, and to enforce any exclusion of limitation of liability of the SHORE consortium partners contained in this Contract and any indemnity in favour of the SHORE consortium partners contained in this Contract.

Amendments and modifications to the text of this Agreement require a separate written agreement to be signed between all Parties. Although this Contract refers to the provisions of the CA and GA, the Beneficiary is not a party to the CA or GA but only bound towards the Coordinator by the CA and GA provisions as referred or reproduced in this Contract.

This Contract is drawn up in English language which shall govern all documents, notices, meetings, and processes relative thereto.

Article 14 - Applicable Law

This Contract shall be construed in accordance with and governed by the laws of Ireland.

Article 15 - Settlement of disputes

If the Contracting Parties are unable to resolve a dispute amicably, such dispute will be finally settled under the Rules of Arbitration of the International Chamber of Commerce by three (3) arbitrators in Dublin.

Each of the Contracting Parties to the dispute shall appoint one (1) arbitrator and the two (2) arbitrators so appointed shall elect the presiding arbitrator. Should a Party to the dispute which should appoint an arbitrator fails to do so within fourteen (14) days of the delivery of the written notice to do so from the other Party to the dispute or should the appointed arbitrators fail to reach agreement on the presiding arbitrator within fourteen (14) days after their appointment, such arbitrator shall be appointed in accordance with the Rules upon request of any of the Parties to the dispute. The seat of arbitration shall be Dublin.

The Contracting Parties agree that the language of the arbitration, including oral hearings, written evidence, and correspondence shall be English.

A duly rendered arbitration award shall be final and binding on the Contracting Parties to the dispute. Each Contracting Party to the arbitration conducted in accordance with this section hereof shall bear its own expenses incurred in connection with such arbitration, including fees of its legal counsels. All other costs and expenses shall be apportioned between the Contracting Parties to the arbitration in accordance with the decision of the arbitrators.

Nothing in this Contract shall limit the Contracting Parties right to seek injunctive relief or to enforce an arbitration award in any applicable competent court of law.

Article 16 – No double funding

By signing this Agreement, the Beneficiary declares to be aware of the fundamental principle underpinning the rules for public expenditure in the EU that no costs for the same activity be funded twice from the EU budget, as defined in the Article 111 of Council Regulation (EC, Euratom) No. 1605/2002 of 25 June 2002 on the Financial Regulation, and confirms that all the work performed under SHORE project

(Grant Agreement no. 101112815) will be done exclusively in the scope of this programme, not being supported or funded by any other European Commission programme.

AS WITNESS:

The Contracting Parties have caused this Contract to be duly signed by the undersigned authorised representatives **in two (2) copies** the day and year first above written:

For Yildiz Technical University (SHORE Coordinator)	For [redacted] [organisation/ individual name] (the Beneficiary)
Mr.Afşın ÇETİNKAYA	Mr/Ms [redacted] [NAME SURNAME]
Prof.Dr.	[redacted]
Signature	[POSITION_IN_ORGANISATION]
	Signature
Done at [redacted] on DD/MM/202Y	Done at [redacted] on DD/MM/202Y

ANNEXES

- **Annex 1: Proposal**
- **Annex 2: Declaration of Honour**
- **Annex 3: Bank Account Information**

SHORE – Open Call # 1

Annex 4 – Applicant Declaration of Honour Template

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APPLICANT DECLARATION OF HONOUR

Project title: _____

Project acronym: _____

On behalf of _____ [organisation name]
established in _____, [Official address], VAT
number _____, represented for the purposes of signing and submitting the
proposal and present Declaration of Honour by _____
[Name of legal representative].

By signing this document, I declare that:

1. I have the power of legally binding the above-mentioned organisation upon submitting this proposal.
2. Neither the above-mentioned organisation nor any linked organisation or any individual member of the proposal team has submitted any other proposal under the SHORE - Open Call #1. In case the above-mentioned organisation or any individual member of the team has submitted more than one proposal to this open call, all associated proposals will be automatically excluded from the evaluation process.
3. I and the above organisation that I legally represent are fully aware and duly accept all SHORE rules and conditions as expressed in the respective open call documents and Annexes and will respect any evaluation decision and proposal selection.
4. All provided information in this declaration is true and legally binding.
5. I give the consent and permission to the SHORE coordinator to use the attached information to contact me for any issue associated with the associated proposal.

Organisation contact information:

Title (Mr., Ms., Dr.)	
Name	
Surname	
Full address	
Country	
E-mail address	
Telephone/ Mobile phone	

DECLARATION OF HONOUR ON EXCLUSION CRITERIA AND ABSENCE OF CONFLICT OF INTEREST

By signing this declaration of honour, I declare that all provided information below is true and legally binding both for me and for the organisation that I legally represent:

1. I declare that the mentioned organisation is not in one of the following situations:
 - a) Is bankrupt or being wound up, is having its affairs administered by the courts, has entered an arrangement with creditors, has suspended business activities, is the subject of proceedings concerning those matters, or is in any analogous situation arising from a similar procedure provided for in national legislation or regulations.
 - b) It or persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been convicted of an offence concerning their professional conduct by a judgment which has the force of res judicata.
 - c) Has been guilty of grave professional misconduct proven by any means which the contracting authority can justify including by decisions of the European Investment Bank and international organisations.
 - d) Is not in compliance with its obligations relating to the payment of social security contributions or the payment of taxes in accordance with the legal provisions of the country in which it is established or with those of the country of the contracting authority or those of the country where the contract is to be performed, to be proved by the deliverance of official documents issued by the local authorities, according to the local applicable rules.
 - e) It or persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been the subject of a judgment which has the force of res judicata for fraud, corruption, involvement in a criminal organization or any other illegal activity, where such illegal activity is detrimental to the Union's financial interests.
 - f) Is subject to an administrative penalty for being guilty of misrepresenting the information required by the contracting authority as a condition of participation in a grant award procedure or another procurement procedure or failing to supply this information or having been declared to be in serious breach of its obligations under contracts or grants covered by the Union's budget.
1. I declare that the natural persons with power of representation, decision-making or control over the above-mentioned organisation are not in the situations referred to in (a) to (f) above.
1. I declare that:
 - a) Neither any person nor I that I know is subject to a SHORE project conflict of interest.
 - b) Neither any person or I that I know participates, controls, submits, or is associated in any way with more than one proposal to the SHORE - Open Call #1
 - c) I have not made false declarations in supplying the information required by participation in the open calls of the SHORE project or do not fail to supply this information.
 - d) I am not in one of the situations of exclusion, referred to in the above-mentioned points (a) to (f).

SHORE – Open Call # 1

Annex 5 – Bank Account Information template

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ACCOUNT HOLDER INFORMATION

Account Name Holder <i>The name or title under which the account has been opened and NOT the name of the authorized agent.</i>	
Holder's Address	
Postcode	
Town/City	
Contact Person <i>Does not need to be an authorised agent.</i>	
Telephone	
Mobile phone	

BANK ACCOUNT INFORMATION

Bank Name	
Branch Address	
Postcode	
Town/City	
Country	
IBAN number / Account number <i>Format example: ES76 2077 0024 0031 0257 5766</i>	
SWIFT code <i>8 to 11 characters</i>	

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Open Call #1

Frequently Asked Questions

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Questions	Answers
Who can apply?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Primary schools or Secondary schools up to ISCED level 3, commonly designated as upper secondary education. See a more detailed explanation here: https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/files/Table_III_Qualifications.pdf Schools which are accredited members of the European Network of Blue Schools at the time of application and provide certificate OR aspire to be members of the European Network of Blue Schools and will demonstrate how they intend to meet the prerequisites to become accredited members by the time of completion of the project.
How to apply for the European Network of Blue Schools?	To apply, click on this link . For more guidelines, check out Handbook for Teachers – European Blue Schools .
Where should the school be established to be eligible?	The school should be legally registered and established in: The Member States (MS) of the European Union (EU) Horizon Europe Associated Countries (check this link) Additionally, it must be located in one out of five targeted regions of the SHORE Open Call - Baltic Sea, Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Rhine and Danube River Area.
What countries are eligible as part of SHORE Target Areas?	Eligible Countries from each target area involve Contracting Parties according to respective conventions governing a specific region (click on the hyperlinked target areas): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Baltic Sea Area: Germany, Poland, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Denmark, Sweden, Finland; Black Sea Area: Romania, Bulgaria, Ukraine, Georgia, Türkiye; Mediterranean Sea Area: Croatia, Cyprus, France, Greece, Italy, Malta, Slovenia, Spain, Tunisia, Albania, Montenegro, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Israel, Türkiye; Danube River Area: Austria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, Germany, Hungary, Moldova, Montenegro, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Ukraine; Rhine River Area: Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, The Netherlands.
What if the applicant's country is based in more than one target area?	If the school is established in the country which is part of more than one target area (e.g., Austria is eligible both in the Rhine and Danube River Area), the applicant should select the area according to the focus and implementation location of their funded activities.
How do schools apply?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Access the website page https://shoreproject.eu/open-calls/ Read the document the Annex 1 - SHORE Guidelines for applicants) Prepare your Annex 2.1 - SHORE Proposal Template. according to the template provided (Available at the above linked website page) Start your online application at the F6S Platform: https://www.f6s.com/shore-open-call-1/apply

	<p>5. Fill the form, upload the template.</p> <p>6. Submit your application.</p>
Until when can the school submit their application?	SHORE Open Call 1 will receive applications by 20 March 2024, 5pm CET.
Can the school submit more than one proposal?	Each school can submit one application and only one project per school will be funded.
The applicant has noticed an error in the proposal after submitting the application. Can they still fix it?	After application submission, editing is not possible. However, If the applicant discovers an error in the proposal and provided the call deadline has not passed, the applicant may request the SHORE - Open Call #1 team to re-submit the proposal (for this purpose please contact us at opencalls@shore.eu with a message titled: RESUBMISSION REQUEST). However, SHORE is not committed that resubmission in time will be feasible in case the request for resubmission is not received by the SHORE team at least 48 hours before the call deadline.
If the school has submitted the application in the previous SHORE Open Call, can it apply again in the subsequent calls?	<p>If the school has applied and has been rejected in the previous open call, it can apply in the subsequent call, but it is mandatory to submit a different or corrected school project proposal and signal it as a resubmission.</p> <p>If the school has applied and has been accepted in the previous open call, then it is not eligible to apply again since the school shall benefit from the financial support to third parties provided under SHORE project only once under one school - one funded project rule.</p>
The school project proposal should focus on topics & subtopics related to blue economy & ocean and water literacy. What are these topics and how to select them?	<p>SHORE Open Call applicants should select at least one topic and subtopic of the open call according to the list proposed in the Annex 1 - SHORE Guidelines for applicants.</p> <p>Applicants are advised to select the most relevant topic and subtopic in line with their proposed activities and regional / local context, eg. environmental challenges. In case more than one topic is relevant, applicants are encouraged to choose the one more suitable for proposed activities.</p>
What kind of activities should the school perform to receive the funding and how many? Can the applicant provide its own suggestions?	<p>The list of the different types of activities for which a school may receive financial support to perform during implementation of the project is available in the Annex 1 - SHORE Guidelines for applicants. The list is fixed and exhaustive, meaning no external additions by the applicant are allowed.</p> <p>Applicants are advised to choose at least one activity from the list and describe it in the Annex 2.1 - SHORE Proposal Template.</p>
SHORE Open Call welcomes proposals submitted by schools, which are open for collaboration/twinning with other blue schools. What type of schools should be involved in this cooperation? Where can the applicant find the co-operator?	<p>The cooperation can be established with schools from the Network of European Blue Schools and those aspiring to become accredited members of the Network of European Blue Schools.</p> <p>To find suitable partners for cooperation/twinning, please refer to the EU4Ocean Platform or eTwinning portal, (Community for schools in Europe for teachers to run on-site or online activities with their students along with colleagues from other European countries).</p>

<p>Can the school bring the collaborator from a previous, similar cooperation?</p>	<p>Yes, the cooperation can already be established, or schools can intend to establish cooperation during implementation of the project.</p>
<p>What should be the subject and format of this cooperation?</p>	<p>In Annex 2.1 - SHORE Proposal Template, applicants are required to describe cooperation activities with other teachers and their students in the format of their choice (on-site or online activities), designed to enable them the exchange of experiences, best practices and successful stories stemming from their blue projects and ocean literacy-driven actions.</p> <p>Twinning can include examples such as capacity building through knowledge sharing, enabling both partner schools to adopt best practices from each other, twinning visits, etc.</p>
<p>What are the requirements regarding carbon neutrality?</p>	<p>SHORE – Open Call #1 is open to schools which participate in climate actions and support values of the European Climate Pact.</p> <p>Additionally, the proposal should demonstrate funded activities having a high degree of circularity, carbon neutrality and positive environmental impact that will be evaluated during the evaluation phase.</p>
<p>How long does the project implementation last?</p>	<p>Selected school projects will last up to 6 months in total.</p>
<p>Besides implementing proposed activities, is there any other task the school should perform such as reporting? What is the content of such reports and how many should be expected from the school?</p>	<p>At the end of the project, the selected school will be required to submit a final report that outlines the activities undertaken in the project, the results achieved, and the lessons learned.</p>
<p>What is the funding?</p>	<p>The total budget per project may not exceed €10,000. The total amount requested can not exceed 100% of the total project costs. The funds will be disbursed in a form of a lump sum.</p> <p>Please summarise the expected project costs in Annex 2.1 - SHORE Proposal Template.</p>
<p>Migrants/Ukrainian citizens - Any specific explanation on how to fulfill this criteria?</p>	<p>At least 20% of the funded proposals must involve migrants or Ukrainian citizens under temporary protection in funded activities. If needed such proposals will be selected from lower ranked positions to meet this quota.</p>
<p>How many times can the school participate in the SHORE programme?</p>	<p>Schools shall benefit from the Financial Support to Third Parties provided under SHORE project only once.</p>
<p>If the applicant has any other questions about the call and the programme, how can they contact the team?</p>	<p>Please send an email to opencalls@shore.eu</p>

SHORE

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